

STUDY OF SYNTHESIS AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF HYDROGELS ENRICHED WITH MINERAL FERTILIZERS

Ibrokhimov M.A.¹, Shirinov Sh.D.², Shirinova O.D.³

^{1,2}Tashkent Scientific Research Institute of Chemical Technology

³Teacher of Department of Ecology and Botany of Andijan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14195822>

Abstract. During this work, the synthesis processes of hydrogels enriched with various fillers were studied, comparing their physical properties with traditional hydrogels.

Keywords: hydrogel, GIPAN, Mixer, Ammonium polyphosphate, IR spectroscopy, Formalin, sulfuric acid.

INTRODUCTION

Today, due to the growth of economic sectors and production in the world, as well as the increase in the population, the water problem is becoming more and more urgent. 70% of the world's population lives in the Eurasian region, which contains 39% of the fresh water on earth. If we take into account that only 40 km³ of the available water reserves of 1.4 billion km³ are suitable for consumption and most of it is in glaciers, it becomes clear how serious the problem is. Because a large part of this water reserve is used for irrigating the land. This figure is 90% in our Republic alone. The fact that the main rivers supplying water to our republic are transboundary rivers shows that the continuity of water supply cannot be guaranteed. A quarter of a century ago, 80% of the water used for the needs of the Republic came from abroad, but today this figure is close to 90%. For this reason, the guarantee of harvesting from irrigated lands in our country remains directly dependent on water supply.

According to the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Management of the Republic of Uzbekistan, until 2000, the low water season was observed once every 6-8 years, but in recent years this process is repeated every 2-3 years. The underground artesian water in the territory of Uzbekistan fully meets the requirements of the state standard, but its use for purposes other than population consumption is not economically feasible.

A lot of research is being done on reducing the amount of water consumed and using water sparingly without reducing the irrigated areas. Due to the geographical location, soil and climate disadvantages, uneven distribution of water resources, the most optimal solution for our Republic is the use of hydrogels.

Hydrogels are superabsorbent polymers created by freely interconnected three-dimensional networks of uniformly distributed flexible polymer chains in a water dispersion medium. From a structural point of view, they are interconnected polyelectrolytes. They have a unique ability to absorb and retain large amounts of water or water solutions relative to their structure as a result of increased entropy within the polymer chain network.

RESEARCH OBJECTS AND METHODS

The synthesis of the synthesized hydrogel containing ammonium polyphosphate was carried out based on the process of obtaining hydrogels based on GIPAN, which is widely used today. The process of synthesizing a highly flexible hydrogel containing ammonium

polyphosphate is carried out as follows: first, GIPAN is put into the reactor, 1/15 of GIPAN is diluted with water, this process is carried out at a temperature of 60-80⁰C for 15-25 minutes. After GIPAN is sufficiently diluted, the temperature rises to 90-110⁰C and is stirred in the reactor for 20-35 minutes with the help of a mixer, then formalin is added to the reactor in the amount of 1/60 of the original GIPAN mass and mixed with the help of a mixer. This process is carried out for 8-10 hours at a temperature of 90-110⁰C. It is very important to control the pH of the solution during the reaction. Due to the presence of -NH₂ and -COONa groups in GIPAN, the environment is strongly alkaline. In this process, if the pH is kept in the range of 6-8, the reaction will give the expected result. In order to keep the pH of the medium in the reactor in the range of 6-8, concentrated sulfuric acid is added to the reactor and neutralized. When the procedure starts, after 6 hours a gel begins to form and it lasts 1-2 hours. The reaction of gel formation proceeds in two stages as follows:

2 hours after the start of gel formation, ammonium polyphosphate is added to the reactor in the amount of 1/20 of the original GIPAN mass, and the process is continued for 15-30 minutes, that is, until the gel and ammonium polyphosphate are completely mixed and come to the same state, then the reactor is stopped.

The reactor is cooled for 10-15 minutes, poured into a ready-made hydrogel container and cooled for 1-1.5 days. A hydrogel is formed. After cooling, the cooled hydrogel is first crushed in grinders and dried in special dryers in order to completely remove the water contained in the cooled hydrogel. In order to make the dried hydrogel easy to use, it is crushed in special grinders and packed in polyethylene film bags in a hermetic state.

The presence of phosphate in the synthesized hydrogel was also confirmed by the SHIMADZU IR spectrophotometer (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Infrared spectrum of hydrogel containing ammonium polyphosphate

Table 1

IQ spectrum analysis of hydrogel containing ammonium polyphosphate

№	Functional groups	Absorption areas
1	CH ₂	2926 sm ⁻¹
2	>CH	2890 sm ⁻¹
3	NH ₂	1640-1550 sm ⁻¹
4	-P=O	1250-1175 sm ⁻¹
5	-P-O-	1190-1150 sm ⁻¹
6	>C=O	1820-1650 sm ⁻¹
7	>CH ₂	1350-1150 sm ⁻¹
8	-C-N-C-	1171-1038 sm ⁻¹

The presence of -P=O is visible in the absorption region of 1158.92 cm⁻¹ in the obtained polyphosphate-preserving hydrogel, the presence of -NH₂ group in the hydrogel is visible in the absorption region of 1558.48 cm⁻¹, the presence of the -P-O- group is visible in the absorption region of 1113.29 cm⁻¹, the presence of the group CH₂ is seen in the absorption of 2927.29 cm⁻¹, the presence of the >S=O group is seen in the absorption region of 1658.48 cm⁻¹, the presence of the >CH₂ group is seen in the absorption region of 1332.81 cm⁻¹, the presence of the -C-N-C- group is seen in the absorption region of 1130.29 cm⁻¹.

The above IQ spectroscopy analysis shows that the presence of -P-O- and -P=O groups in the synthesized hydrogel, therefore, the presence of NH₂, CH₂, >S=O groups proves the presence of a phosphate group in the synthesized hydrogel.

We compared the physical and chemical properties of the synthesized hydrogel containing ammonium polyphosphate with traditional hydrogels (Table 2)

Table 2

Physical and chemical properties of hydrogels

№	Hydrogels	Physical properties		
		Color	Degree of swelling	average swelling period (minutes)
1	Starch-based hydrogel	White	100-120	35-65
2	Hydrogel based on acrylic acid	White yellow	110-125	60-180
3	Hydrogel containing ammonium polyphosphate	White yellow	125-143	60-220

Based on the data in Table 2, it can be said that the hydrogel containing ammonium polyphosphate has a higher degree of swelling compared to the analog hydrogel. The low rate of rotting has a great effect in agriculture. In addition, hydrogels containing phosphate decompose over time and serve as plant fertilizer, $-NH_2$ groups in the gel also decompose and enrich the soil with nitrogen. In a word, flaming hydrogel decomposes over time and does not cause any harm to the environment.

REFERENCES

- Ramli, R.A.; Lian, Y.M.; Nor, N.M.; Azman, N.I.Z. Synthesis, characterization, and morphology study of coco peat-grafted-poly(acrylic acid)/NPK slow release fertilizer hydrogel. *J. Polym. Res.* 2019, 26, 266. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Zhang, W.; Liu, Q.; Xu, Y.; Mu, X.; Zhang, H.; Lei, Z. Waste cabbage-integrated nutritional superabsorbent polymers for water retention and absorption applications. *Langmuir* 2022, 38, 14869–14878. [CrossRef\]](#)
- Feng, L.; Yang, H.; Dong, X.; Lei, H.; Chen, D. pH-sensitive polymeric particles as smart carriers for rebar inhibitors delivery in alkaline condition. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 2018, 135, 45886. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Gao, L.; Wang, S.; Zhao, X. Synthesis and characterization of agricultural controllable humic acid superabsorbent. *J. Environ. Sci.* 2013, 25, S69–S76. [\[CrossRef\]](#) [\[PubMed\]](#)
- Kratochvílová, R.; Sedláček, P.; Pořízka, J.; Klučáková, M. Composite materials for controlled release of mineral nutrients and humic substances for agricultural application. *Soil Use Manag.* 2021, 37, 460–467. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Nnadi, F.; Brave, C. Environmentally friendly superabsorbent polymers for water conservation in agricultural lands. *J. Soil Sci. Environ. Manag.* 2011, 2, 206–211.
- Pushpamalar, J.; Langford, S.J.; Ahmad, M.B.; Lim, Y.Y.; Hashim, K. Eco-friendly smart hydrogels for soil conditioning and sustain release fertilizer. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 2018, 15, 2059–2074. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Azeem, M.K.; Islam, A.; Khan, R.U.; Rasool, A.; Qureshi, M.A.R.; Rizwan, M.; Sher, F.; Rasheed, T. Eco-friendly three-dimensional hydrogels for sustainable agricultural applications: Current and future scenarios. *Polym. Adv. Technol.* 2023. (first published). [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Omirova, R. Z., Bolysbek, A. A., Shirinov, Sh. D., Dzhililov, A. T. Synthesis and research of polymer hydrogels on the basis of hydrolysed polyacrylonitrile and epichlorhydrin. *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*, (2019). 12(4), 2047-2051. [\[CrossRef\]](#)

10. Д.Ш Шеркузиев, МО Юсупов, М.М Курбонов, Ш.Д Ширинов Управление земельными ресурсами и их оценка: новые подходы и инновационные решения. Материалы российско-узбекской научно-практической конференции, посвященной 2019. Том 100., Страницы 603-605
11. Холназаров Б.А Тураев. Х. Х., Ширинов Ш. Д., Джалилов А. Т. Синтез гидрогеля на основе крахмала и акриловой кислоты //Композиционные материалы научно-технический и производственный журнал. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Omirova, R. Z., Bolysbek, A. A., Shirinov, Sh. D., Dzhalilov, A. T. Development of complex fertilizer technology with improved agrochemical properties using hydrogel. Rasayan Journal of Chemistry, (2020). 13(1), 733-738. [[CrossRef](#)]